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Characteristics of a Planar SOFC With Load Variation

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Abstract

Renewable energy such as solar power and wind power has been widely introduced to mitigate environmental impacts in energy consumption, but it needs power output leveling for demand. SOFCs can be a candidate for the component thanks to their high efficiency. However, load variation for the leveling gives rise to time variation in distributions of fuel/oxidant concentration, current, and temperature in a cell, affecting the power output stability and the durability of a cell. We have therefore developed a finite element method model of a planar SOFC verified with measurement using segmented electrodes (Figs.1, 2) (1), (2), and investigated corresponding cell behavior assumed in a model of a stationary combined heat and power (CHP) system (3) and limitation of load variation for durable cell/interconnector designs and operating conditions.

Fig.1. Segmented cathode of the planar SOFC

Fig.2. Experimental set-up

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Introduction

Renewable energy such as solar power and wind power has been widely introduced to mitigate environmental impacts in energy consumption, but it needs power output leveling for demand. SOFCs can be a candidate for the component thanks to their high efficiency. However, load variation for the leveling gives rise to time variation in distributions of fuel/oxidant concentration, current, and temperature in a cell, affecting the power output stability and the durability of a cell. We have therefore developed a finite element method (FEM) model of a planar SOFC verified with measurement using segmented electrodes (1-4), and investigated corresponding cell behavior assumed in a model of a stationary combined heat and power (CHP) system (5) and limitation of load variation for durable cell/interconnector designs and operating conditions.

1. Finite Element Modeling

COMSOL Multiphysics (COMSOL, Inc.) was used to develop an FEM model to obtain the hydrogen partial pressure, current and temperature distributions in an anode-supported cell (1,2). Butler-Volmer type kinetic equation and Ohm's law were used for the charge conservation. We employed the Stefan-Maxwell equation for the multicomponent diffusion, the Navier-Stokes equation for non-porous fluid in the gas stream, and the Brinkman equation for fluid in the porous electrodes (1, 2). FEM modeling was carried out for a single channel (width: 2 mm, depth: 0.5 mm) and rib (width: 2 mm) of the anode and cathode separators in a co-flow configuration.

2. Experiments

2.1 Cathode segmentation

We have applied segmented electrode method that cathode was segmented into three parts of upstream, midstream, and downstream parts (1-4) to a planar SOFC (ASC-10B, Elcogen, Estonia) consisting of a Ni/8YSZ (8mol%YSZ) anode support, an LSC cathode, an 8YSZ electrolyte, and a GDC interlayer. The anode geometrical area was 19.5 (6.5×3.0) cm² while the cathode geometrical area was 2.25 (1.5×1.5) cm² each in the upstream, midstream and downstream parts. In this study, we mainly focus on the current and partial pressure distributions in the anode, so that only the cathode were segmented to prevent the influence of the anode segmentation on the fuel flow in the in-plane direction. The anode and cathode separators made of stainless steel (Crofer 22 APU, VDM Metals GmbH, Germany) had flow channels with a width of 1 mm and a depth of 1 mm (MAGNEX Co., Ltd., Japan). The anode separator had 8 parallel flow channels having a length of 4.9 cm. Silver paste (Silvest P-248, Tokuriki Honten Co. Ltd., Japan) and mesh (Nilaco Corp., Japan) were used for current collection.

2.2 Current-voltage measurement

Three electronic loads were used to measure current-voltage (IV) characteristics under voltage control so that each segmented electrode had the same potential (equipotential) to reproduce a normal single cell condition (1-4). Temperature of the cell was 650°C at open circuit voltage (OCV) using a tubular electric furnace. For the measurement, four-terminal

method was used, where the current and voltage lines were separated. After reduction of the anode, IV measurements were carried out with feeding dry H₂/N₂ mixture (H₂: 17 cm³min⁻¹, N₂: 7 cm³min⁻¹ (at 25°C, 1 atm)) and air (air: 100 cm³min⁻¹ (at 25°C, 1 atm)). Current density and cathode separator temperature transients were measured in the upstream, midstream and downstream parts.

3. Results

Figure 1 shows a transient response of the current density derived from the FEM modeling with stepwise changes of the cell voltage at constant fuel and air flow rates.

Fig. 1. Time variation of the current density and outlet temperatures derived from the FEM model with the cell voltage change (a) from 0.850 V to 0.843 V (output power from 100% to 120%) and (b) from 0.850 V to 0.856 V (output power from 100% to 80%).

Fuel and air utilizations are 70% and 37.2 %, respectively at 0.85 V, an output power of 100%. The cell voltage changes were assumed in conjunction electrically and thermally

(uniform heat flux through the separators) with a CHP system model (5) using a process simulator, Aspen Plus so that the output power became 120% (0.843 V) and 80% (0.856 V). The current density with the voltage drop spikes within 0.5 s and then transitions to a steady-state (Fig. 1(a)). A similar spike in current drop appears with the voltage rise (Fig. 1(b)). These spikes can be explained similarly as chronoamperometry reflecting current transient response represented by the Cottrell equation corresponding to local hydrogen partial pressure variations (6). It is interesting to note that a slight increase in the current density can be seen after the spike with the voltage rise owing to more uniform current distribution along the flow channel with decreased overpotential.

Figure 2 shows the transient response of the current density with the cell voltage changed in a stepwise manner from 0.85 V to 0.75 V and from 0.75 V to 0.85 V in the IV measurement.

Fig. 2. Current transient along the anode flow channels with the stepwise voltage changes (a) from 0.85 V to 0.75 V and (b) from 0.75 V to 0.85 V at 650°C. (H₂: 17 cm³min⁻¹, N₂: 7 cm³min⁻¹ (at 25°C, 1 atm)) and air (air: 100 cm³min⁻¹ (at 25°C, 1 atm)). Both the voltage drop (Fig. 2(a)) and the voltage rise (Fig. 2(b)) give current spikes in each part along the anode flow channels, reproducing and verifying the FEM modeling.

Acknowledgments

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